

2015

AUG-SEP

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education
Research Journal (AMIERJ)***

***(Bi-Monthly)
Peer-Reviewed Journal
Impact factor: 2.125***

V O L - I V I s s u e s : V

Chief-Editor:

Ubale Amol Baban

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF MARKS OBTAINED AT THE B.ED.EXAMINATION

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Abstract :

This present paper reports the analytical study undertaken the relationship between practical and theory marks of teacher students. The practical marks is related to teacher educators attendance and punctuality, teacher educators attitude and methodology in teaching, teaching-learning process, teacher students performance and student teacher feedback, student educator and students teacher evaluation. There obtains a very close correlation between a conclusion that might somewhat modify these who are septic about giving weight age to internal assessment as lacking reliability. The total 80 B.Ed. student teachers of this college were selected by stratified random sampling. Obtain marks out of 600 in university examination were taken as external and obtain marks out of 600 in college examination as internal evaluation. Findings were derived on the base of objectives, hypothesis, statistical analysis

Key words:

Assessment, Evaluation, Examination, Teacher students, feedback internal marks, and Theory examination marks, weight age of practical marks.

Introduction:

The training institution is concerned with the development of trainee teacher in all round development of his physical, social and emotional, teaching knowledge, skills, and personality qualities. During the process of the teacher training of the teacher students has to be continually appraised with regard to the level of his intelligence, attainment, aptitude and interest and the method of teaching-learning, various skills to be adopted. The traditional system of examinations which primarily measures the academic achievements. Several research studies are being made to bring to light the drawbacks of this system so that remedial steps can be taken.

The weight age given to the internal marks in the final evaluation of a student teacher achievement and performance in one such step. In examination and measurement the emphasis is upon includes all the changes that take place in the development of a balanced personality and measure the qualities of teacher students. The researcher to investigate the relationship between

Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

(Bi-Monthly) Peer-Reviewed Journal Vol No IV Issues V
AUGUST-SEP 2015 ISSN 2278-5655

the final theory examination and internal marks in various practical's. The scheme of examination in the B. Ed. Degree course is as under

Theory Course

Course	Name of the Subject	Internal	External	Total
EDU 501	Foundations of Education	20	80	100
EDU 502	Pedagogical Knowledge	20	80	100
EDU 503	Secondary Education and Classroom Management	20	80	100
EDU 504	Learning Resources and Evaluation	20	80	100
EDU 505	English, Marathi, Hindi, Mathematics	20	80	100
EDU 506	History, Geography, Science, Commerce	20	80	100
	Total	120	480	600

All the papers carry 100 each and each section carry 50 marks .In the six papers all the marks assigned at the annual examination. Practical related to six theory Paper is 120 marks assigned by the teacher educators.

Practicum

EDU :507 School Based Experiences	Marks
a. Initiatory School Experiences (10 Days)	60
b. Internship Programme	50
EDU:508 - Practice Teaching Competency	
a. Micro-Teaching (5+5 Lessons)	20
b. Integrated Lesson (1 Lesson)	05
c. Lesson Planning Workshop & Demonstration Lessons	10
d. Simulated Teaching (1+1 Lessons) Each Method	20
e. Stray Lessons (6+6) & 5+5 in Internship Programme	110
f. Workshop on Constructivist Approach to Teaching (Planning of 1 lesson)	20

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AUGUST-SEP 2015 ISSN 2278-5655

g. Workshop on Preparation of Teaching aids	30
h. Lesson Observations (Micro = 10, Bridge = 2, Demonstration =7 ,Simulation = 4, Constructivism=2, ICT =2, Models =2,Stray Lessons = 31 Total =60)	60
i. Workshop On ICT Based Lessons (Planning of 1+1 lessons)	20
J. Workshop on Models of Teaching (Planning of 1+1 lessons)	20
EDU: 509 Development of Language and life skill	20
EDU:510 Project Work	10
a. Action Research Workshop (Preparation of Proposal)	
b. Project related to Community Experience	20
c. Physical Education Workshop	15
EDU:511 Evaluation	
a. Diagnostic Test on Content Knowledge and Remedial Programme	
b. Workshop on Comprehensive and Continuous Evaluation	20
c. Twelve assignments (Two Open Book Assignment)	20
d. External Viva	50
e. Internal Examination	20
Total	600

The teaching profession requiring through knowledge as well as practical skills. Teacher students work with the physical body. The training is totally related to practical work. Practical work develop the teacher students work with the complex of the human mind and personality. The practical work is based on long established learning theory such as feedback, guidance, demo, reinforcement, were adopted.

Objectives:

- 1.To compare the internal and theory examination marks of student teacher.
- 2.To study the student teacher attitude towards practical and theory examination.
- 3.To study the Internal and External evaluation of B.Ed. student teachers.
2. To know the correlation between Internal and External evaluation of B.Ed. Student teachers.
3. To study the Internal and External evaluation of B.Ed. student teachers in context of their faculty.
4. To know the correlation between Internal and External evaluation of B.Ed. students teachers in context of their faculty.

Research Sample-

For the present study the purposive sampling method was used for the selection of the sample consisted statistical Analysis of Marks Obtained at The B.Ed. Examination (2015) of S.M.T. Government College of Education. The Details of Sample results as follows

Table 1: Sampling data

Total	Exam. Appear	First Class with Distinction	First Class	Second Class	Fail
80	77	7	55	7	8

Table 1 shows that out of 80 students 77 were appearing the B. Ed. Examination. The percentage of Appearing examination is 99.25. In this Examination 7 students got first class with distinction out of 77 and 55 students teacher obtained first class.

Graph 1: Shows the student teacher result

Graph 1 shows the result of student teacher in B. Ed. Examination held in March 2015 .

Analysis under different aspects:

The achievement of student teacher obtained i) EDU 501 :Foundations of Education ,ii) EDU

502 Pedagogical Knowledge, iii) EDU 503 :Secondary Education and Classroom Management ,
iv) EDU504:Learning Resources and Evaluation, v) EDU 505: Pedagogical Content Knowledge
and Methodology,(Marathi, Hindi, English, Sanskrit, General Science, Commerce) vi) EDU
506: Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Methodology(History, Geography, Mathematics,
Economics)

Table 2: Course wise mark of student-teacher

Sr No	Seat No	i	ii	iii	iv	v	vi	Total	i	ii	iii	iv	v	vi	Total	Practicum	TT	%	Result
Theory								Sessional work											
1	182	53	63	55	55	53	63	342	16	16	14	15	15	18	94	451	887	73.92	Pass
2	183	42	24	49	38	66	44	263	16	16	13	14	15	16	90	446	799	66.58	Fail
3	184	52	48	52	48	53	65	318	17	17	15	15	14	17	95	464	877	73.08	Pass
4	185	54	51	47	45	66	60	323	16	15	13	14	16	15	89	443	855	71.25	Pass
5	186	0	39	36	33	55	47	210	15	15	14	14	16	17	91	430	731	60.92	Fail
6	187	50	43	53	43	60	49	298	16	15	14	13	15	14	87	435	820	68.33	Pass
7	188	53	63	53	46	52	60	327	15	15	13	15	15	16	89	406	822	68.50	Pass
8	189	42	34	42	41	45	52	256	17	17	13	13	18	14	92	460	808	67.33	Pass
9	190	52	41	49	44	42	50	278	16	17	15	13	14	17	92	445	815	67.92	Pass
10	191	52	48	53	49	46	64	312	16	16	15	15	16	14	92	443	847	70.58	Pass
11	192	56	49	50	47	52	59	313	16	18	14	15	18	17	98	469	880	73.33	Pass
12	193	54	45	46	42	55	59	301	15	15	13	14	15	16	88	389	778	64.83	Pass
13	194	45	33	47	37	63	50	275	16	16	13	13	15	17	90	463	828	69.00	Fail
14	195	50	44	51	43	50	52	290	17	17	13	14	15	14	90	453	833	69.42	Pass
15	196	49	45	51	44	53	56	298	17	16	15	16	15	15	15	460	773	64.42	Pass
16	197	41	40	42	35	55	47	260	16	16	14	13	18	16	93	422	775	64.58	Pass
17	198	57	57	52	46	68	50	330	17	17	15	15	16	16	96	473	899	74.92	Pass
18	199	37	36	44	36	45	56	254	17	16	13	16	16	14	92	455	801	66.75	Fail
19	200	30	37	46	35	41	45	234	16	16	13	16	18	14	93	462	789	65.75	Fail
20	201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00	
21	202	52	54	50	40	58	61	315	17	17	15	16	15	14	94	484	893	74.42	Pass
22	203	49	45	44	42	60	59	299	17	16	13	16	18	15	95	472	866	72.17	Pass
23	204	44	40	44	40	62	49	279	16	17	14	16	16	16	95	444	818	68.17	Pass
24	206	56	40	47	42	62	47	294	15	15	13	14	17	14	88	438	820	68.33	Pass
25	207	62	52	57	44	63	62	340	16	16	13	15	18	18	96	474	910	75.83	Pass
26	208	59	40	46	43	61	55	304	15	16	14	13	16	16	90	436	830	69.17	Pass
27	209	50	45	48	44	62	56	305	17	18	14	16	18	14	97	468	870	72.50	Pass
28	210	33	41	39	43	55	49	260	17	18	13	13	18	13	92	485	837	69.75	Fail

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29	211	49	42	45	46	62	57	301	15	15	14	15	16	16	91	427	819	68.25	Pass
30	212	54	48	54	47	62	52	317	16	15	13	15	16	14	89	427	833	69.42	Pass
31	213	46	41	47	44	43	44	265	16	15	13	14	13	16	87	427	779	64.92	Pass
32	214	59	51	50	45	42	62	309	16	14	14	13	13	17	87	401	797	66.42	Pass
33	215	49	46	44	45	43	57	284	16	16	13	13	13	17	88	439	811	67.58	Pass
34	216	44	45	45	44	62	52	292	16	16	12	14	16	13	87	454	833	69.42	Pass
35	217	47	47	43	44	64	55	300	17	17	14	13	15	16	92	456	848	70.67	Pass
36	218	56	52	47	45	61	52	313	17	16	13	14	18	13	91	475	879	73.25	Pass
37	219	54	47	40	40	53	55	289	15	14	13	13	16	16	87	409	785	65.42	Pass
38	220	59	52	47	43	65	48	314	16	14	15	13	16	15	89	449	852	71.00	Pass
39	221	41	33	40	27	49	46	236	16	16	14	14	17	16	93	425	754	62.83	Fail
40	222	51	41	47	48	52	54	293	16	16	15	15	15	12	89	443	825	68.75	Pass
41	223	61	56	45	44	64	58	328	16	16	13	14	16	16	91	437	856	71.33	Pass
42	224	58	59	53	50	47	62	329	17	15	13	14	14	15	88	443	860	71.67	Pass
43	225	63	56	54	54	62	64	353	18	18	16	15	18	14	99	503	955	79.58	Pass
44	226	54	48	46	45	60	60	313	16	15	13	15	16	16	91	441	845	70.42	Pass
45	227	55	46	44	42	45	54	286	16	18	14	15	14	17	94	465	845	70.42	Pass
46	228	43	43	46	41	42	54	269	15	16	15	14	16	16	92	434	795	66.25	Pass
47	229	57	50	51	49	52	59	318	17	18	15	15	18	17	100	483	901	75.08	Pass
48	230	56	50	47	46	42	63	304	17	17	14	15	15	18	96	465	865	72.08	Pass
49	231	59	50	47	41	67	59	323	16	17	13	14	16	18	94	456	873	72.75	Pass
50	232	54	49	52	48	60	52	315	17	17	15	16	18	15	98	491	904	75.33	Pass
51	233	56	47	51	46	43	48	291	16	16	14	14	13	16	89	459	839	69.92	Pass
52	234	49	45	45	40	63	56	298	16	18	16	17	16	16	99	485	882	73.50	Pass
53	235	56	55	50	52	58	60	331	16	17	15	16	16	15	95	460	886	73.83	Pass
54	236	50	44	45	46	60	55	300	15	17	13	15	18	18	96	444	840	70.00	Pass
55	237	53	50	45	34	44	61	287	15	17	13	15	16	17	93	454	834	69.50	Pass
56	238	43	34	40	42	62	43	264	13	14	13	14	15	16	85	395	744	62.00	Pass
57	239	58	50	56	53	69	61	347	17	18	16	17	17	16	101	491	939	78.25	Pass
58	240	58	59	50	55	62	59	343	16	17	14	14	18	13	92	458	893	74.42	Pass
59	241	46	40	33	40	52	51	262	17	17	14	15	18	15	96	465	823	68.58	Pass
60	242	41	48	35	46	52	54	276	16	16	14	14	16	16	92	427	795	66.25	Pass
61	243	45	44	40	44	61	56	290	16	17	15	16	18	14	96	443	829	69.08	Pass
62	244	50	46	52	49	61	58	316	17	16	16	17	17	14	97	474	887	73.92	Pass
63	245	37	44	31	47	37	49	245	16	14	14	17	15	15	91	424	760	63.33	Fail
64	246	30	40	30	39	40	41	220	16	15	13	15	14	14	87	402	709	59.08	Fail
65	247	50	41	50	48	65	58	312	16	16	15	17	18	17	99	467	878	73.17	Pass
66	248	50	46	50	53	44	51	294	16	18	12	12	13	16	87	432	813	67.75	Pass
67	249	49	47	49	55	45	59	304	17	18	13	15	14	16	93	465	862	71.83	Pass
68	250	41	40	45	40	48	40	254	16	16	15	15	18	14	94	464	812	67.67	Pass

69	251	46	34	49	41	50	49	269	16	16	14	16	15	15	92	426	787	65.58	Pass
70	252	53	56	60	55	67	62	353	17	18	16	16	16	18	101	485	939	78.25	Pass
71	253	50	42	45	44	59	50	290	16	16	14	14	15	17	92	405	787	65.58	Pass
72	254	51	36	49	40	55	51	282	15	16	13	13	18	13	88	421	791	65.92	Pass
73	255	45	36	49	40	50	54	274	16	16	14	17	16	15	94	464	832	69.33	Pass
74	256	43	41	46	40	65	60	295	15	15	14	15	16	15	90	417	802	66.83	Pass
75	257	41	34	47	43	40	57	262	16	17	13	14	17	17	94	457	813	67.75	Pass
76	258	53	51	55	53	49	60	321	17	17	15	14	15	17	95	448	864	72.00	Pass
77	259	40	40	40	42	52	55	269	17	17	15	15	18	18	100	483	852	71.00	Pass

The average scores for individual class also show that there is a big gap among first class, which may be related with the ethos of study. so that although this comparison is not exact, it is closely approximate.

Graph 2 : Course –wise Student teacher result

The result of theory examination and practical marks of each teacher-students were then calculated and statistical analysis was done for further analysis were defined. The mean of course is as follows

Table 3 : Mean of all course

Sr. No.	Course	Mean
1	EDU 501 :Foundations of Education	64.30
2	ii) EDU 502: Pedagogical Knowledge	60.70
3	iii) EDU 503 :Secondary Education and Classroom Management	60.00
4	iv) EDU504: Learning Resources and Evaluation	58.00
5	v) EDU 505: Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Methodology, (Marathi, Hindi, English, Sanskrit, General Science, Commerce)	69.80
6	vi)EDU 506: Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Methodology(History, Geography, Mathematics, Economics)	69.20

Graph 3 : Mean of all course

The teacher-students were studied and sessional work of each paper is support to increase the marks of this Each course. The mean of all theory papers marks is in between 58.00 to 69.00. The practical experience is basically related to theory papers.

Conclusion –

The teacher-students come into the profession and as existing teachers learn more and develop new ideas. The teacher training is of a highly complex which requires considerable knowledge a wide variety of skills and positive attitudes. The interesting point here is that teacher educators who carry out course planning in a teacher-students group frequently derive from experience of personal relationship and the practical work in groups. The complex nature of present day teacher-training means that the work of a teacher-educator and teacher students is no longer simply that of an teacher profession. The statistical analysis of the examination results of materials research methods course was carried out. The results indicate that the distribution of examination scores approximate to normal distribution. It is noted that there is a big gap among first class student teacher and second class passed . Difficulty of the exam paper belongs to median level, and discrimination of this is qualified as well as reliability.

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